

EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOL REGULATION IMPLEMENTATION TO IMPROVING STUDENT DISCIPLINE IN HIGH SCHOOL

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Abstract:

In today's society, discipline is the first step in recognizing the characteristics and behavior of a person in society. Cultivating a sense of discipline can be done since school, especially in high school (SMA) through school regulations. However, students often do not obey the rules at school which causes students to be undisciplined and school regulations to be ineffective. This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of school regulations on student discipline through student perceptions of school regulations, factors that influence student discipline, and the impact of school regulations on school regulations at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang. The research method used is qualitative with data collection techniques through observation, interviews, and documentation. The population in the study came from class XI IPA 1 at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang with 30 respondents and a sample of 10 respondents. The data analysis techniques used are data reduction, data display, and conclusions and verification. The results of the study show that school regulations at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang are effective in fostering student discipline at school by 70%. This study shows that school regulations can have a major impact on student discipline at school. Therefore, St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang needs to evaluate school regulations, socialize school regulations to students, hold regular discussions regarding school regulations with students, and involve students in the process of revising school regulations.

Keywords: school rules, student discipline, high school, st. albertus catholic high school, malang

INTRODUCTION

In today's society, discipline is the first step in recognizing a person's characteristics. Discipline can be interpreted as a form of a person's

compliance with the rules that occur in society. Discipline is often a reference for society to assess a person's behavior in socializing, or in accepting new employees. Because of the importance of discipline in people's lives, educational

institutions in Indonesia implement discipline in the environment of the institution.

Educational institutions that are the basis for a person's discipline education are through elementary to high school. School is an institution designed for teaching students or pupils under the supervision of educators or teachers (Simarmata, 2023). School is not just a place to seek knowledge, but as a place to train student discipline in the school environment. By training discipline in the school environment, students will find it easier to learn discipline under the supervision of teachers and schools.

The implementation of schools in implementing student discipline in the school environment is through written and unwritten school regulations or often referred to as rules of order. Rules of order are regulations that are prepared by the school and must be implemented (St. Albertus Catholic High School Tatibsi book compilation team, 2023). School regulations also include sanctions if students violate these regulations. The number of school regulations is quite large, so schools take further action to formulate these regulations in the form of a book of rules of order. One of the books of rules that reference for the researcher's research is the 2023/2024 Tatibsi Book (Book of Rules and Achievements) of St. Albertus Catholic High School.

The Rules and Achievements (Tatibsi) book essentially contains various rules of conduct for students at St. Albertus Catholic Senior High School, Malang. The Rules and Achievements book contains the rules of conduct for students at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, intended as a guideline for action (rules of conduct) carried out by students during the educational process at school (St. Albertus Catholic High School compilation team, 2023). With the

presence of the Rules and Achievements book for students at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, students can be helped in the process of character formation and become honest, kind-hearted, cultured, disciplined, hard-working, hopeful, and caring individuals who foster a spirit of prayer, brotherhood, and service. This Rules and Achievements book can also be a guideline for students to behave more maturely and establish relationships with others.

But in reality, the rules in the school rules are ignored by the students themselves. Students often do not care about the importance of school rules for themselves. In fact, the school that has made the school rules has set points of violation in each of its rules. Violation points are minus points obtained by students if they violate the rules (St. Albertus Catholic High School Tatibsi book compilation team, 2023). It can be seen that the school rules made by the school are not effective for students with many students violating these rules.

Based on the explanation above, the researcher is interested in conducting a survey on students of St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang about the effectiveness of implementing school regulations in improving student discipline. The author will describe this in a research proposal entitled "Effectiveness of Implementing School Regulations in Improving Student Discipline in Senior High Schools (Study of the effectiveness of school regulations on SMAK St. Albertus Students, Malang)".

The formulation of the problem used as a guideline in this study are: 1) How are students' perceptions of the implementation of regulations at St. Albertus Catholic High School? 2) What are the factors of the effectiveness of the implementation of school regulations in improving student discipline at St.

Albertus Catholic High School? 3) What is the impact of the implementation of regulations on the learning environment and school atmosphere at St. Albertus Catholic High School?

The purpose of this study is to fulfill the following: 1) To identify and analyze the factors that influence the effectiveness of school regulations in improving student discipline at St. Albertus Catholic High School, 2) To understand the impact of implementing school St. Albertus Catholic High School, 3) To evaluate the impact of implementing school regulations on the learning environment and school atmosphere at St. Albertus Catholic High School.

The benefits of this research are divided into two, namely theoretical benefits where this study can provide a broad understanding of the benefits of school regulations and their relationship to student discipline. This study can strengthen the theoretical basis, especially the effectiveness of school regulations in student discipline. As well as practical benefits, where this study has practical benefits, such as: 1) For researchers, the results of this study are expected to increase knowledge about education and discipline, and provide new perspectives for further research, 2) For students, the results of this study are expected for students to better understand the importance of discipline, which can help them behave better at school, and 3) For schools, the results of this study are expected so that schools can use the results of the study to evaluate existing policies or regulations and make improvements if necessary.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research used in this study is a study conducted by Hasan (2018) from the Islamic religious education study program, Faculty of

Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, State Islamic Institute (IAIN) Kediri with the title "Effectiveness of School Regulations in Improving Student Discipline at SMA Negeri 6 Kediri City". This study focuses on the effectiveness of school regulations in improving student discipline at SMA Negeri 6 Kediri City. The conclusion in this study is that the regulatory sanction system carried out at SMA Negeri 6 Kediri City uses violation points and direct punishments. The effectiveness of the regulations at SMA Negeri 6 Kediri City in this study is quite good but needs to be improved because students have not obeyed school regulations.

Second, Rodhiyah et al. (2018) conducted a study on the implementation of school policies related to student disciplinary violations in an effort to shape student character at SMA Negeri 7 Kediri. The results of the study showed that the policy had a positive impact on reducing the level of violations among students. Student behavior began to reflect good character, such as discipline, respect for applicable legal norms, responsibility, and creating a more conducive school atmosphere. In addition, the relationship between students and between teachers and students is getting closer. Several factors that support this policy are effective communication between the disciplinary party and the homeroom teacher, so that students can always be supervised. However, there are also several obstacles, such as the lack of student awareness of the importance of order and limitations in existing administration.

Third, Aditya Kristian (2022) conducted a study on the implementation of a point system as an effort to improve student discipline and ensure that violations of rules are handled fairly. Each violation has a different point value, and students who collect 100 points will be

expelled from school. Handling of violations is carried out based on the accumulation of points, namely the first coaching is given after reaching 30 points, the second coaching at 50 points, and the third coaching at 75 points. The results of the study showed that the point system at SMA Negeri 5 Tana Toraja showed that this system was effective in improving student discipline, with a decrease in the number of violations having a positive impact on time discipline, dress, and behavior. However, there are still a small number of students who continue to violate the rules.

Fourth, Nurfadillah et al. (2022) conducted a study on the implementation of rules at SMAN 2 Soppeng through various socialization steps, such as during the acceptance of new students, delivery of rules in flag ceremonies, and posting posters in each class. The school involves all educators and education personnel in supervision, while sanctions are given in the form of reprimands. The purpose of these rules is to regulate student behavior and improve their discipline. However, there are several challenges in its implementation, including students' lack of understanding of existing rules, low awareness to obey the rules, differences in character among students, the influence of the external environment, lack of effective supervision, and the existence of social interests within the school.

Fifth, Nevi Pebriyani (2022) conducted a study on the causes of students not obeying school rules at SMAN 10 Jambi. This study focuses on factors that influence students' disciplinary behavior at school. The results of the study showed that the factors causing student indiscipline consist of several aspects. From family factors, 33.7% of respondents reported a lack of parental supervision, attention to education, and disharmonious relationships within the family. From the

school side, 30.5% of respondents stated that the implementation of rigid regulations, dislike of school or lessons, and lack of teacher motivation affected discipline. On the other hand, 35.8% of respondents identified environmental factors, such as the influence of friends, lack of parental supervision of socializing, weakness in religious education, and the absence of positive means to fill free time, as causes of indiscipline.

The similarity of this study with previous studies is taking the theme of the effectiveness of school regulations in improving student discipline, the theoretical basis of effectiveness and similar school regulations, and the use of qualitative research methodology in the study. However, the difference between this study and previous studies is the difference in the implementation of the study, the time of the study, the purpose of the study, and the products produced from the study. The product of the previous study was in the form of a final thesis, while the product in this study is in the form of a research report and infographics on two different courses.

According to the Great Dictionary of the Indonesian Language, the word "effectiveness" comes from the root word "effective," which means having an effect, influence, or impression that is efficacious and effective, and can bring success. In this context, effectiveness is defined as the result of achieving the goals that have been attempted. H. Emerson, as quoted by Soewarno Handayani (1994:16), states that "effectiveness is a measurement in the sense of achieving previously determined goals." In this study, effectiveness is measuring how school regulations are successfully implemented by the school as the achievement of previously planned goals.

According to Rifa'i in the book *Sociology of Education* (2011; 140)

Regulations are a procedure from a certain agency to regulate and align needs with a party. Regulations are useful for mental and physical development, foster respect and can develop character for someone who obeys them. As stated by Hurlock in Haryani (2013) that "regulations function as guidelines for children's behavior as a source of motivation to act as a social expectation". Hurlock in Haryani (2013) also argues that "discipline is expected to be able to educate children to behave according to the standards set by social groups by inviting and forcing them, punishment for violators of regulations and rewards for behavior that is in line with regulations"

Discipline in schools is a concrete effort made to ensure that the attitudes and mentality of students...students become good and do not deviate from the prevailing norms. The disciplinary process can be done by making rules that have been agreed upon together in the school area or environment. The role of school regulations as a guideline that regulates student behavior such as educating and fostering student behavior so that they have the desired disciplined character. School regulations contain requirements that must be implemented by students and prohibitions that contain actions for students who violate them.

Discipline is a self-awareness that comes from within to follow and obey the rules, values, and laws that apply in a particular environment. Discipline has an important role in influencing, encouraging, controlling, changing, fostering, and forming certain behaviors in accordance with the values that are instilled, taught, and exemplified. A disciplined attitude aims to prevent deviant behavior and things that can interfere with the learning process. Through discipline, students are trained to build habits of doing good actions and are able to control each

of their actions, so that students will be obedient, compliant, and orderly in teaching and learning activities.

Student discipline is an important aspect in creating an effective learning environment, where various forms of discipline can be observed in their daily behavior. The following are forms of discipline in schools: 1) Discipline in behavior. Discipline in behavior refers to the attitudes and behavior of students that demonstrate compliance with the rules and norms that apply in the school environment. Such as not bringing/consuming alcoholic beverages. 2) Discipline in neatness. Discipline in neatness refers to the attitude of students to maintain neatness and order in their appearance and learning environment. Such as not coloring/dyeing hair. 3) Discipline in crafts. Discipline in crafts refers to the attitudes and behavior of students that demonstrate responsibility in completing academic tasks. Such as not being late for school. 4) Discipline in cleanliness. Discipline in cleanliness involves the active participation of students in maintaining the cleanliness of the school environment. Such as not littering. 5) Discipline in the teaching and learning process. This discipline includes student compliance in the learning process in the school environment, such as preparing and/or bringing cheat sheets.

Senior high school is a form of formal education that provides general education at the secondary education level as a continuation of Junior High School. The function of secondary education is to develop values and attitudes of beauty and harmony, knowledge, abilities, and skills as preparation for continuing to higher education and/or to live in society in order to achieve national education goals. While the goals of secondary education are to increase faith and piety, live healthily, expand knowledge and art, have expertise

and skills, become responsible members of society, and prepare students to follow further education.

St. Albertus Catholic High School Malang is a catholic school located at Jl. Talang No.1, Oro-oro Dowo, Klojen District, Malang City, East Java. St. Albertus Catholic High School Malang, as an educational institution that lives the charism of the Carmelite Order under the Sancta Maria Foundation, has three main tasks in the spirituality of students, namely prayer, brotherhood, and service. St. Albertus Catholic High School Malang has a vision to make St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang a community of intellectual learning leaders who are also hearted, disciplined, hardworking and full of hope. Meanwhile, the mission of St. Albertus Catholic High School Malang is: 1) Organizing teaching and learning activities that foster the soul of learners, 2) Organizing character building activities that prepare leaders who are hearted, cultured, disciplined, hardworking, full of hope, and care about the environment, and 3) Organizing spiritual building activities that foster a spirit of prayer, brotherhood, and service. In addition to focusing on academic development, St. Albertus Catholic High School Malang also provides: Albertus Malang also prioritizes non-academic development which is a characteristic of the school itself with various achievements at home and abroad.

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used in this study is qualitative research. Qualitative research is a qualitative research method is a research method based on philosophy used to research in scientific conditions (experiments) where researchers as instruments, data collection techniques and qualitative analysis emphasize more on meaning (Sugiyono, 2018).

The type of qualitative research analyzes the object of research through social activities and the object's perception of the problem being studied. The reason the researcher uses qualitative techniques is to examine students' perceptions of the effectiveness of school regulations on student discipline at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang.

Data collection techniques in this study are conducting observations, interviews, and documentation. An interview is a conversation with a specific purpose conducted by two parties, namely the interviewer who asks questions and the interviewee to provide answers to the questions given (Sugiyono, 2018). The subjects to be interviewed by the researcher are students selected by the researcher or the school at random. Observation is one method of data collection by observing or reviewing carefully and directly at the research location to find out the conditions that occur or prove the truth of a research design that is being carried out (Syafnidawaty, 2020). Observations in this study were carried out in classes that had been determined by the researcher or the school at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang. Documentation is a record of past events in the form of pictures, photos, sketches and others (Sugiyono, 2018). Documentation is very important for research because documentation is evidence of the research process. Documentation that is a reference in research is books, photos, videos, and others.

The data used in this study are the results of interviews with students of St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang. The data were collected directly in class with a total of 32 students with a total of 30 respondents. However, in this study, the researcher used a sample of 10 respondents from the 30 respondents

collected.

The primary data sources used in this study are: 1) The main informants, namely students randomly selected by the researcher or the school at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, 2) The 2023/2024 Rules and Achievement Book (Tatibsi) of St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, 3) Research documentation during the researcher's observations at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang.

The secondary data source used in this study is information on the summary of student violations at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, which will be the researcher's research material in formulating interview questions.

The location of the research conducted by the researcher is at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, located at Jl. Talang No.1, Oro-oro Dowo, Klojen District, Malang City, East Java (65112). St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang is precisely adjacent to Jalan Talang, south from St. Albertus Boys Dormitory, north of Tanggamus 31 Restaurant, and approximately one kilometer west of the Church of the Blessed Virgin Mary of Mount Carmel (Malang Cathedral) and approximately 2.6 kilometers south of Brawijaya University, Malang. The researcher deliberately chose this location to facilitate accurate data collection.

The research instruments of this study were by conducting observations, interviews, and documentation. The procedures used by researchers in conducting interviews (Yunus, 2010) were: 1) Researchers introduced themselves to the research subjects, 2) Researchers explained the purpose of the Researchers' arrival to the research subjects, 3) Researchers explained the interview material to the research subjects and 4) Researchers asked questions to the

research subjects. The procedures used by researchers in conducting observations (Syafnidawaty, 2020) are: 1) Researchers determine the object of research observation, 2) Researchers create observation guidelines or research frameworks, 3) Researchers determine the location of research observations, 4) Researchers determine the data collection method to be collected, and 5) Researchers determine the method of analyzing research data. Researchers conduct documentation in class as a complement to the output to be produced by the researcher, namely the creation of infographics, and research reports. Researchers take pictures during the research process, resulting in a research logbook. (Look at table 1)

The research design used in this study is phenomenology. Phenomenology can be interpreted as the study of a person's life experience or a method for studying how individuals subjectively feel experiences and give meaning to the phenomenon (Kirana, 2021). Phenomenology comes from the research subject's awareness of the research problem and the research subject's experience of the problem phenomenon in the research. Thus, researchers can conclude the research subject's perspective on the research problem.

The stages of data analysis techniques used in this study are: 1) Data Reduction, by identifying themes (finding the main theme of respondents' answers related to the implementation of school regulations and their impact on student discipline), coding (grouping data into certain categories. For example, answers about discipline can be grouped based on aspects such as behavior, neatness, diligence, and cleanliness), and eliminating irrelevant information (deleting data that does not support the

research objectives so that the focus remains on important information).

2) Data display, by means of analysis results (displaying analysis results to illustrate the relationship between the implementation of school regulations and student discipline visually), descriptive narrative (compiling a narrative that explains the findings from the interview with direct quotes from respondents to provide context and strengthen the results of the analysis), and thematic summary (compiling a summary based on the themes that have been identified, so that the results of the analysis can be easily understood), 3) Conclusions and verification, by drawing conclusions (concluding how effective the implementation of school regulations is in improving student discipline based on existing findings), verification of findings (ensuring that conclusions are supported by valid data by comparing interview results with previous literature or research), reflection and recommendations (reflecting on the research process and providing recommendations for educational practices or further research based on the findings).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of research results conducted by researchers in the field was carried out using interview, observation, and documentation methods. The focus of this study was to determine the perceptions, factors, and impacts of school regulations on student discipline in senior high schools at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang students. Data analysis was carried out through the process of data reduction, data presentation, verification, and drawing conclusions. The following are the results of the study described in detail.

Based on the results of the study,

the majority of students at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang stated that the school regulations were quite clear and easy to understand. This is due to the systematic documentation in the student code of conduct book, which functions as a comprehensive guide containing details of the regulations, sanctions, and procedures that must be followed. The existence of this book makes students feel more confident in carrying out their daily activities because they understand and know what is expected of them. Understanding these regulations has a positive effect on student compliance, making them aware of the limits and consequences of violations. However, there are a small number of students who consider some regulations to be too complicated and restrict freedom of expression.

Furthermore, the majority of students also think that the sanctions applied for violations of the rules are appropriate and proportional. They feel that the sanctions are consistent with the provisions in the rules book, which creates understanding and comfort with the sanction mechanism. Clarity and consistency of sanctions are considered important to create a disciplined and safe environment, as well as to encourage respect for the rules. However, some students feel dissatisfied and consider some sanctions to be inappropriate for the type of violation, arguing that minor actions sometimes get too severe sanctions, while more serious violations do not always get commensurate consequences. This can create a sense of injustice and affect students' motivation to comply with the rules.

Most students acknowledged that school regulations have a positive impact on the teaching and learning atmosphere, creating a more conducive environment. They felt that having clear rules regarding

discipline, attendance, and behavior in class contributed to an atmosphere that supports the learning process. However, there were also students who felt that the impact of the regulations was not significant. Some of them showed resistance to regulations that were considered too strict or did not suit their needs, which could reduce the effectiveness of the regulations in supporting learning.

In addition, observations showed several types of violations that were often committed by students. First, violations related to crafts, such as not bringing the discipline book, were detected in seven to ten students out of a total of 30 students observed, indicating that students' understanding and attention to discipline still need to be improved. Second, violations of attendance, especially being late to school, occurred in four to seven students, which could have a negative impact on the teaching and learning process. In addition, there were two students who did not participate in extracurricular activities, indicating that motivation was needed so that students would be more active in participating in activities outside the classroom. Finally, serious violations including receiving two warning letters (SP) occurred in four students, indicating that there were serious problems that needed to be addressed so that they did not impact students' discipline and academic achievement.

Finally, some students expressed that the school rules were considered too strict and not relevant to their needs. They argued that the rules interfered with the learning process and created psychological stress. In addition, students felt that these rules limited the school experience and hindered social interaction, especially with the ban on mobile phones that prevented them from documenting important moments. Students also criticized the rules

related to hair appearance, which were considered unclear in explaining cause and effect, which could lead to confusion and estrangement in the relationship between students and teachers.

In an effort to understand student discipline at St. Albertus Catholic High School, Malang, the results of the study showed that teachers play a very important role in helping students comply with school regulations. Teachers not only provide direction and guidance, but also supervise student activities and provide sanctions if necessary. The firm nature of teachers contributes to creating respect for regulations, which ultimately improves student discipline. If teachers are not active in implementing regulations, then the regulations will not run effectively.

On the other hand, the majority of students stated that the role of school friends is very large in helping them obey the rules. School friends can provide a positive influence by reminding each other to obey the rules. However, there are also students who feel that the role of friends is negative, because some of them can encourage them to break the rules. This shows that the social environment of students has a big influence on their behavior at school.

Furthermore, the observation results show that the sanctions applied by the school have a significant role in encouraging student discipline. Consistent and fair sanctions can provide a deterrent effect to students who violate. However, there are also students who feel that sanctions do not have a significant effect, some even tend to underestimate the rules. This shows the need for an evaluation of the effectiveness of sanctions applied in schools.

Most students, around 70%, felt that school regulations had a big influence on their learning environment. Regulations were considered to shape

students' character and create good habits needed in school life. However, 30% of students felt that the regulations were only helpful enough without having a significant impact. This shows that although regulations are important, their implementation needs to be adjusted to the dynamics of students' needs.

School rules provide many benefits to students, from creating an orderly environment to increasing focus on learning. Complying with the rules also helps students develop discipline and a sense of responsibility. In addition, students who are disciplined at school tend to be more adaptable to rules in the social world and college in the future. However, there are students who feel that the existing rules are not always relevant to their needs, so adjustments need to be made to increase their effectiveness.

Examining the impact of school rules shows that they play an important role in improving student discipline. Observations show that rules not only serve to regulate behavior, but also help students manage their time and increase their sense of responsibility. With teacher supervision and consistent enforcement of rules, students become more aware of the consequences of their actions. The majority of students, around 80%, stated that rules help them prepare themselves as individuals with good character, which is very important for developing useful discipline in the future, both in college and in the workplace.

However, regarding learning motivation, there are various opinions among students. Some students feel that the rules motivate them to learn, while others feel the opposite. This indicates that the rules need to be carefully designed.

so that it does not only have one function as a control tool but also to increase students' enthusiasm for learning. In addition, school regulations also serve

as a means to strengthen the relationship between students and teachers. Most students feel that regulations create positive interactions. However, there are groups of students who feel that some regulations do not fit in, which can cause tension in the relationship.

In terms of long-term impact, the rules implemented in schools have a major influence on student discipline in college and the workplace. Students who are accustomed to discipline in the school environment tend to be better prepared to face the rules in the professional world. However, some students expressed that the existing rules are sometimes less relevant to their needs, so adjustments are needed so that school rules better reflect the reality of the outside world.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been conducted, the results of observations show that school regulations have a significant role in shaping students' discipline, responsibility, and character. Most (majority) students feel that the existing regulations are clear enough and effective in creating a conducive learning atmosphere. School regulations are also considered useful for preparing for challenges in the world of college and work, especially in building character discipline and the ability to adapt to the environment. In addition, the existence of sanctions is considered to provide a deterrent effect that makes students more careful in behaving and acting. School friends are also recognized as having an important role in helping students to comply with school regulations.

However, in fact, not all students have a positive view or agree with the rules set by the school. Some students feel that certain rules, such as the prohibition of mobile phone use and hair rules, are too strict and irrelevant to their needs. This of

course causes students to become stressed and reduces their comfort in living school life. In addition, a small (minority) of students' opinions expressed that the sanctions applied were sometimes not in accordance with the violations committed, thus creating a sense of injustice and they also felt that school rules did not really affect learning motivation. This shows that although school regulations have great goals and benefits, there are still gaps to be evaluated so that they can be accepted and implemented effectively.

In order to improve the effectiveness of the regulations, schools are advised to re-evaluate the rules that are considered too strict or less relevant. For example, providing certain flexibility regarding the use of mobile phones in special situations or outside of school hours. The sanction system also needs to be improved by adjusting the type of sanction based on the level of violation to provide a sense of justice. In addition, socialization regarding the rules is needed to improve communication between teachers and students regarding the imposition of sanctions, so that the reasons behind the decision can be understood and well accepted by students.

To help students understand and increase their sense of discipline regarding the importance of obeying a regulation, schools can hold regular discussions involving students, this aims to make them aware of the benefits of the regulation. Finally, involving students in the process of evaluating and revising regulations can make the rules more relevant to their needs, without forgetting or ignoring the values of discipline that are to be achieved. Thus, the steps listed in this suggestion are expected to ensure that school regulations do not only to improve discipline, but also to create a comfortable environment and support student development.

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ENCLOSURE

Table 1. Indicators and questions questionnaire/interview.

Nomor	Indikator	Pertanyaan
1	Persepsi	Apakah Anda merasa peraturan di sekolah cukup jelas dan mudah dipahami? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
2		Bagaimana pandangan Anda mengenai sanksi yang diberikan ketika melanggar peraturan? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
3		Apakah peraturan sekolah berdampak terhadap suasana belajar mengajar di sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
4		Sejauh yang anda lihat, peraturan apa yang sering dilanggar oleh anda ataupun teman anda di sekolah? Jelaskan alasan mengapa melanggarnya? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
5		Bagaimana pandangan anda mengenai peraturan yang menurut anda terlalu ketat atau tidak relevan dengan kebutuhan siswa? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
6	Faktor	Menurut anda, Seberapa besar peran guru anda dalam membantu Anda mematuhi peraturan sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
7		Menurut anda, Seberapa besar peran teman sekolah anda dalam membantu anda mematuhi peraturan sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
8		Menurut anda, Seberapa besar peran sanksi yang diberikan oleh pihak sekolah yang dapat membantu anda mematuhi peraturan sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
9		Menurut anda, Seberapa besar pengaruh peraturan sekolah terhadap lingkungan belajar anda di sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
10		Menurut anda, Seberapa besar manfaat yang anda terima jika mematuhi peraturan sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
11	Dampak	Menurut Anda, apakah peraturan sekolah membantu meningkatkan kedisiplinan Anda? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
12		Apakah Anda merasa adanya peraturan sekolah membantu Anda dalam mempersiapkan diri menjadi individu yang berkarakter

		baik sesuai semangat DEMPO (Doa, Egaliter, Melayani, Pekerja Keras, Optimis-Penuh Harapan) dan karisma Karmel (Doa, Persaudaraan, dan Pelayanan)? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
13		Menurut anda, apakah peraturan sekolah dapat memotivasi anda untuk semangat belajar di sekolah? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
14		Apakah peraturan sekolah dapat membantu anda dalam mempererat relasi antara siswa dan guru? Jelaskan pendapat anda!
15		Menurut Anda, apakah peraturan sekolah memberi dampak besar pada kedisiplinan anda nantinya di dunia perkuliahan dan dunia kerja? Jelaskan pendapat anda!

Table 2. Ten sample respondents' biodata and answers to questionnaire/interview questions

Nama	Kelas	Jurusan	Persepsi no.5	Faktor No.3	Dampak no.2
Fiona Fiesta Dania Valenty	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	Akan mengganggu pembelajaran dan pastinya siswa merasa tertekan dan tidak bisa menikmati masa sekolahnya yang harusnya ia dapatkan disekolah contoh kenangan saat di kelas tidak ada karena tidak diperbolehkan main hp	Sangat besar, mungkin (belum pernah kena pelanggaran)	iyaa betull sekali
Cherlyn Angela Halim	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	Kurang ada manfaatnya karena tidak relevan.	Besar karena siswa akan takut terkena sanksi.	Iya karena peraturan itu bisa membuat kita lebih baik.
Margareta Kesyha Caitlin Tanggu	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	menurut saya peraturan di dempo aman aman saja.	sangat besar, karena saya tidak ingin malu saat memakai rompi oren jadi saya memilih untuk patuh.	Ya, karena saya lebih banyak belajar tentang semangat DEMPO dan karisma Karmel
Griselda Elysia M	11 (17-18 Tahun)	IPA	Peraturan yang terlalu ketat atau tidak relevan dengan kebutuhan siswa bisa menghambat kreativitas dan	Sanksi dari pihak sekolah berperan penting dalam menjaga kepatuhan terhadap peraturan, karena	Ya, peraturan sekolah membantu saya mempersiapkan diri menjadi individu

			perkembangan mereka.	memberikan konsekuensi nyata bagi pelanggaran.	berkarakter baik sesuai semangat DEMPO dan karisma Karmel.
Andrea Lynn Caralee	11 (17-18 Tahun)	IPA	menurut saya peraturan yang terlalu ketat adalah pada saat saya SMP yaitu tidak boleh menggunakan gelang karet, membuat siswa merasa tidak nyaman dan makin tidak bersemangat untuk sekolah	cukup besar karena membuat kita takut melakukan hal tersebut kembali	iya, karena sekolah memberikan pengajaran dan fasilitas yang berhubungan dengan karisma karmel dengan baik
Darryl Hizkia	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	Tidak baik, karena siswa rawan tidak disiplin	Besar karena sanksi yang besar memberi efek jera juga	Iya, dengan peraturan tsb kita bertumbuh dan berproses
Albertus Ryu Feivel Tan	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	terlalu mengekang anak sehingga susah/takut untuk melakukan sesuatu	menurut saya adalah sanksi sebaiknya poin prestasi di kurangi saat melakukan pelanggaran agar mereka memikirkan bagaimana caranya agar mendapat poin prestasi yang lebih banyak	tidak juga
Rein Vianno Soendoro	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	Ya seharusnya peraturan yang terlalu ketat dapat membuat hubungan antar guru dan siswa menjadi kaku.	Sangat karena tanpa sanksi maka murid tak akan menyesal atas kesalahannya.	Ya tentu saya merasakan perkembangan karakter selama bersekolah di Dempo.
Reyner Yudea Siregar	11 (17-18 Tahun)	IPA	peraturan yang terlalu ketat dan tidak relevan dapat membuat murid malas dan trauma untuk belajar	sangat membantu	ya sedikit berguna untuk mengingatkan tentang peraturan

Fidelis Eferata Wijaya	11 (15-16 Tahun)	IPA	contohnya seperti rambut tidak boleh gondrong, itu tidak relevan karena rambut tidak akan mengganggu proses pembelajaran	besar, agar siswa tidak melanggar peraturan lagi	membantu
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Picture 1. Effective and ineffective percentage of school regulations on student discipline